

SND Policy for Persistent Identifiers (PID) on Research Data

Date: 2021-09-28

Version: 3 (translation)

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Swedish National Data Service

snd.gu.se

(+46) 31-786 10 00

snd@gu.se

SND, University of Gothenburg,

Box 463, 405 30 Gothenburg, Sweden

It is essential that we can identify and cite¹ research data in a simple and reliable way. Users² of the SND research data catalogue shall be able to trust the origin and reliability of data objects in the catalogue. Attaching a persistent identifier (PID) to data is an important part of the work with FAIR data. Persistent identifiers on research data are a prerequisite for certification of digital data repositories and a common requirement from many scientific journals and research data portals.

This PID Policy applies to research data (datasets) with metadata that are findable in the SND research data catalogue. It has been approved by the SND Steering Committee and is implemented on new catalogue entries as of 26 May 2020.

1. All research data described in the SND catalogue from 2020 onward shall have received a PID. This also applies to data where metadata are harvested to the SND catalogue from other catalogues/portals. Exceptions can be made until 31 December 2023³ in cases where the SND catalogue entry describes and links to resource collections (e.g., databases, catalogues, portals) which contain several datasets.
2. A global PID service⁴ shall be used when the PID is issued. The PID shall lead to a website,⁵ a so-called landing page, which shall contain information about provenance, version, accessibility, and possible limitations to use.
3. Metadata for research data shall include a suggested data citation.⁶ The suggested citation shall include a PID.
4. New or altered versions of research data shall receive a new PID and older versions shall be saved to enable citation of specific dataset versions. Therefore, the new PID shall contain a reference to the previous version PID. Research data should not be deleted. If a dataset is deleted, the landing page shall be saved, with information about the reason for the data deletion and a possible link to the current version of the deleted dataset.

¹ Research data are digital material that can form the basis of a scientific analysis, regardless of research field.

² Users signifies both researchers who have created new data and reusers of existing data.

³ At this date, the resource collections can be transferred to Researchdata.se.

⁴ A global PID service is a service that is permanently accessible, even for computers (machine actionable), and which has a system for automated redirection to new landing pages when they are created. Some examples of PID services are: DOI, Handle, ARK, PURL, URN, etc.

⁵ The landing page can be an entry in the SND research data catalogue or in an external catalogue/website.

⁶ An example of a suggested citation:

Name Surname. HEI, Institution (year). Dataset title. Swedish National Data Service. Version 1.0. <https://doi.org/10.5878/0000-0000>